

2022 Mills Prize *continued*

Twenty remarkable books were nominated for the 2022 Mills Prize. A full list of all titles nominated for the 2022 William Mills Prize, including those titles that were shortlisted, is available on the [Polar Libraries Colloquy website](#).

The William Mills Book Prize is awarded every two years and honours the best Arctic or Antarctic non-fiction books published throughout the world. The prize was first presented in 2006. It is named in honour of William Mills, a polar librarian and author, and a core member of the Polar Libraries Colloquy during its formative years.

For more information, please contact Julia Finn at millsprize@gmail.com

Decolonization of Arctic Library and Archives Metadata (DALAM) Thematic Network Update: January 2023

by **Sandy Campbell**

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When we last reported to readers of the PLC Bulletin on DALAM's progress¹, we were at the point of having proposed the network to University of the Arctic (UARctic) and were anticipating its introduction at PLC 2022 in Quebec City. DALAM was approved as a UARctic Thematic Network in June of 2022. Four days later at PLC, Dr. Sharon Farnel presented the first in-person DALAM sponsored workshop on decolonizing metadata. The session was well-attended, with more than 20 participants. Many participants reported being at the beginning of the decolonization process in their archives and libraries.

Since the Colloquy, DALAM has offered two more training activities. In September, Brian Stearns and Fairfax Culpepper, of the University of Alberta Library presented an on-line session on Technical aspects of implementing decolonized subject headings at the University of Alberta Library and in January, 2023, Sharon Farnel presented an online version of her Decolonizing Metadata workshop.

As a UARctic Thematic Network, DALAM has a [UARctic sponsored web-page](#) where the organization is described, and activities, members,

and publications and presentations are listed. The web-page is also linked from the [PLC Partnerships page](#).

DALAM is led by Susanna Parikka (University of Lapland and Chair of the PLC Steering Committee), with Shannon Christoffersen (Arctic Institute of North America) and Sharon Farnel (University of Alberta) as vice-leads. The network is actively seeking an Indigenous co-lead. Members meet monthly, either to advance the business of the network or for an educational activity.

DALAM membership is open to all PLC members or any information professional working in a UARctic institution. For further information about the network and/or membership, contact Sandy Campbell: sandy.campbell@ualberta.ca

¹ Campbell, S. (2022, Spring). Introducing DALAM: A Proposed UARctic Thematic Network. *Polar Libraries Bulletin*, (85), 3. <https://polarlibrariescolloquy.files.wordpress.com/2022/06/spr-2022-plb-final-5-30-2022.pdf>